

MODELING OF DISTRIBUTED HETEROGENEOUS SUPERCOMPUTER SYSTEMS OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Bondarchuk V.,

candidate of technical sciences,

Head of the Department of Visual Pattern Recognition,

Ivanova S.,

Director,

Kravchenko N.

candidate of technical sciences,

senior researcher, senior researcher,

department of visual pattern recognition,

Institute for Artificial Intelligence Problems, Donetsk

Abstract

The article is devoted to the development of promising IT technologies for operation in industrial clusters of the economy, their application for the needs of a group of companies. The article presents studies that provide a new solution to the problem of developing the management of the information-analytical process based on distributed heterogeneous supercomputer systems of socio-economic development

Keywords: information-analytical systems, standard forms of analytics, Implementation Controllers, inter-connection, functional modules.

Introduction. The current stage of socio-economic development is the time of digital transformation of all sectors of the economy, the interaction of platforms of digital twins of participants in this process. The purpose of scientific research is the development of promising IT technologies for operation in any clusters of the economy, their application for the needs of a group of companies. The article presents studies in which a new solution is given to the problem of developing the management of the information-analytical process on the basis of distributed heterogeneous supercomputer systems of socio-economic development.

Problem analysis. The basis of modeling is new IT technologies for developing and debugging complex technical systems, modeling software modules for automated control systems for the information and analytical process of distributed heterogeneous systems in order to control the life cycle of the system, make decisions and optimal control.

The architecture of a structured computer network, the configuration of a server, a central office workstation has been developed; functions of processes on servers; equipment for docking the server and workstations; recommendations for choosing equipment for connecting departments to the Internet; requirements for primary and secondary database servers, replication schedule [1, pp. 39]

A set of measures has been designed to ensure the safety of data in a multiservice supercomputer network. Technologies of RAID arrays; Executive Diskkeeper v7.0, RAID controller, Active Directory, NTFS permissions for information resources, group policy sections at the domain level, divisions, virtual private network; flexible tool for determining user rights in the system; centralized management of measures for anti-virus protection of workstations [2, pp. 82].

Schemes of a structured computer network, configuration of a server, a workstation of a central office are presented; functions of processes on servers, equip-

ment for docking a server and workstations; recommendations for selecting equipment for connecting departments to the Internet, requirements for the primary and secondary database servers, replication schedule. The project is designed to solve the following subtasks: supercomputer network of the central office, 20 ministries and 40 enterprises of the Republic; description of the active equipment for docking the server and workstations; substantiation and selection of equipment for connecting departments to the Internet; description of requirements for the primary and secondary database servers, replication schedule [3, pp. 26].

Experience in the development and implementation of digital platforms, multi-service automated control systems and automated workstations for applied purposes allows us to solve new urgent problems. An innovative project aimed at supporting the industrial sector, integrates monitoring information and analytical systems, forms analytics typical for industrial activities.

Web application lifecycle include events: page initialization, device adapter detection when generating page output; to improve performance, the adapter is cached, so it is looked up once for each user agent; loading view state; loading page return data; loading custom code; sending notifications about changes to the returned form data; user events are not generated at this stage; processing the form return event, the page executes the code associated with the event that caused the form return; pre-rendering, the code gets the last opportunity to make any changes., pagination is performed, the page output is generated taking into account the pagination parameters; saving the view state, the page state is serialized into a string, which is then stored - usually as a hidden field, user events are not generated at this stage; page rendering, the page generates output that will be sent to the client, the adapter is responsible for displaying child controls in the right order; page unloading, at this stage the device adapter performs the necessary final operations.

Results. Automated workplace for analytical processing of text data is designed to support application-oriented analytics forms typical for industrial activities. The integration of monitoring information and analytical systems was carried out thanks to tools and hardware and software systems in relation to the industrial sector of the economy based on the use of a spatial cluster model. The proposed innovative project is implemented on the basis of an exogenous and endogenous cluster model of machine learning, software agents, forms methods of directed selective generation of a heterogeneous distributed information resource, indexing of monitoring results, focused on the semantics of textual information, systematization of text-containing information objects in a distributed heterogeneous information resource, architectural organization of storage data of predominantly text type.

The functional model of the industrial information system includes a set of tasks: registration of industrial enterprises and users with a set of rights; input and editing of data about the enterprise and types of products; preparation of texts of statements of various types; sending applications to the MIT (Ministry of Industry and Trade); work with applications received by the MIT; preparation of texts of documents (conclusions, orders); formation and display of registers of enterprises, industrial products and conclusions on the production of products on the territory of the republic; formation of an extract from the register of industrial products; Editing system directories.

The system inputs are: data on enterprises and users entered by employees of the ministry who are granted the rights to register users of the system; information about the enterprise and manufactured industrial products (addresses of production facilities, name and brief description of the types of products and their corresponding codes of scientific and industrial production, codes of the commodity nomenclature of foreign economic activity, information on standardization documents, export directions of products of this type), which are entered into the system by a representative of the enterprise; information about decisions made by employees of authorized departments of the ministry on applications from product manufacturers.

System output: generated texts of applications of various types (application for the issuance of an opinion on the production of products on the territory of the DPR, an application for the exclusion of products from the register, for inclusion in the register of exporters, etc.); receipts on acceptance of documents; texts of documents (conclusions, orders, notifications) prepared based on the results of processing applications from enterprises; registers of enterprises, industrial products, issued conclusions on the production of products; extracts from the register of industrial products.

The control elements of the system are: user authentication algorithms in the system; algorithms for controlling the information entered by the user before sending it to the server; algorithms for recording / updating information in the database; search algorithms in the database for information requested by the user; algorithms for generating output documents in PDF and DOCX formats; Algorithms for data backup and recovery.

The mechanisms of the system are: open source server platform Node.js; PostgreSQL DBMS; express library (web framework for Node.js applications); ORM-library sequelize (a tool for interaction between the Node.js platform and relational databases); officegen library (creation of documents in MS Office formats); library node-schedule (task scheduler); dotenv library (working with environment variables); crypto library (secure cryptographic algorithms); read-excel-file library (reading data from MS Excel files); pdfkit library (generation of documents in PDF format); AngularJS (open source JavaScript framework).

Conclusion. The information-analytical process has been formalized, a model for determining compliance with functional requirements has been formulated, which allows for implementation. Controllers (Table 1) provide a "communication" between the user and the system, control and direct data from the user to the system and vice versa, use the model and view to implement the required action. The innovation project has good prospects for further development, incl. commercialization of activities, which is especially important for the socio-economic development of the Republic.

Fig.1 - Structural diagram of the interconnection of the functional modules of the system

Table 1

Implementation Controllers	
Controller Name	Corresponding Application Page
addIndustryCtrl.js	Adding an entry to the directory of industries
addSubdivCtrl.js	Adding an entry about the MTI subdivision
adm_addStreetCtrl.js	Adding a street entry to the directory
adm_addUserCtrl.js	Registering an MTI employee user as an administrator
adm_baseController.js	System Admin Page
adm_cityDistrictListCtrl.js	List of administrative districts in the city
adm_cityListCtrl.js	List of cities and administrative regions (of republican subordination)
adm_cityDistrictListCtrl.js	List of administrative districts of the city
adm_cityPlusListCtrl.js	List of cities with subordinate settlements
adm_countryListCtrl.js	Viewing the list of countries
adm_kvedListCtrl.js	Viewing the list of foreign economic activity codes
adm_nppListCtrl.js	Viewing the industrial item code reference
adm_streetListCtrl.js	Viewing the street guide
adm_tnvedListCtrl.js	Viewing the directory of codes of the commodity nomenclature of foreign economic activity
adm_usersCtrl.js	List of users - MIT employees
changeCtrl.js	User password change
eo_scanConcCtrl.js	Page for attaching a scanned copy of the conclusion
eo_viewConclusionsCtrl.js	Viewing a list of completed conclusions
eo_viewRequestsCtrl.js	View submitted applications
exitCtrl.js	Sign out confirmation
indListCtrl.js	Directory of industries
inpAddressCtrl.js	Address Entry Page
lk_addProductCtrl.js	Page for entering / editing data on the type of product
lk_addRequestCtrl.js	Preparation of an application for the issuance of a conclusion / exclusion of products from the register
lk_addRequestExpCtrl.js	Preparation of an application for inclusion in the register of exporters
lk_companyCtrl.js	Entering / editing data about the enterprise

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